

THE DEVELOPMENT OF NOVEL COMPOSITE SANDWICH STRUCTURES WITH INTEGRATED SHOCK ABSORBING FUNCTIONALITY

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ABSTRACT

The strategic replacement of the stiff core with compliant cellular materials in regions of a composite sandwich panel has the potential to integrate a shock absorbing functionality into an otherwise rigid structure. This work describes the development and preliminary analysis of 3D printed thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) energy absorbing cellular architectures.

A parametric study was undertaken to assess the compressive behaviour and energy absorbing characteristics of potential cellular inclusions with both hexagonal and multi re-entrant, auxetic topologies. In our study, we investigate the effect of varying the size and internal angles of unit cells on the compressive response of the global arrays, up to strains of 75%.

Samples are loaded globally and locally in compression with flat plates and cylindrical indenters, respectively; the cell collapse behaviour for both cases are captured. The energy absorbing capability of the macroscopic cellular structures was analysed through the generation of a series of energy absorption diagrams derived directly from the stress-strain curves obtained.

In our study, it was found that by varying the loading conditions on the 3D printed polyurethane cellular arrays, the cell buckling modes could be controlled, with the promotion of different collapse behaviour leading to unique energy absorption profiles, at large elastic strains. This study has shown the potential for novel 3D printed architectures for energy absorption. The ongoing effective characterisation of material and structure will ultimately facilitate in the design of recoverable, hyperelastic cellular structures with energy absorption profiles tailored to specific impact events.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of lightweight, high stiffness composite sandwich panels is desirable in the construction of high speed marine craft since minimising ‘inertia’ whilst maximising ‘rigidity’ allows for optimum boat performance. However, if the dynamic loads that the craft are subject to in harsh operating environments are not attenuated, the structural performance may exceed that of the human operator. In cases where the use of add on damping solutions are impractical or not possible, it is desirable to integrate areas of targeted energy absorption within the structural components themselves. This work is part of the larger study for the development of composite sandwich panels with shock absorbing functionality and details early stage characterisation of elastic cellular structures, which will replace regions of sandwich panel core, allowing for tailored panel flexure and targeted energy absorption.

Cellular solids formed from elasto-plastic materials are capable of efficiently absorbing energy at a relatively constant stress via the progressive buckling of cell walls through the structure [1-3]. Such solids include open cell packaging foams and paper honeycombs whose energy absorbing potential are widely utilised in the packaging industry [4]. However, due to the non-reversible nature of the energy absorption process, elasto-plastic cellular solids are unsuitable for protection of systems from repeated impact events. In contrast, cellular materials formed from hyperelastic materials have the potential to absorb energy from repeated impact events, primarily via cell wall buckling, entirely within the elastic regime. The compressive stress strain curve for a generic hyperelastic cellular structure is shown in Figure 1 which shares the same characteristic profile of that of an elasto-plastic cellular material, but without plastic deformation contributing to energy absorption within the plateau region. By varying the cellular architecture of a hyperelastic cellular structure, the plateau region can be manipulated; via intelligent structural design, the energy absorption profile may be tailored to predefined impact/vibrational profiles. The shape and magnitude of the energy absorption profile for the compression on any cellular structure is dependent of the mode of buckling and collapse.

Figure 1: Compressive stress strain curve for an elastic cellular structure. Energy absorbed per unit volume is shaded, with useful energy absorbed in the plateau region at relatively constant stress

Low strain behavior of hexagonal cellular structures and their buckling modes under different uniaxial compressive loading conditions have been subject to analysis via classical beam-column end-moment behavior [5, 6] and finite element analysis [6]. Up until recently, analysis that extended beyond this small elastic strain analysis has focused only on buckling and plastic collapse behavior [2, 3]. Over the last few years however, interest in the large strain behavior of hyperelastic macroscopic cellular structures has significantly increased due to their potential, not only for energy absorption, but also as potential as their use for creating metamaterials with tailorable photonic/phononic or hydrophobic/hydrophilic properties [7] and structures which can tuneably control the propagation of elastic waves through their structure [8]. The majority of work thus far has focused on the deformation patterns achievable under large compressive strains, with Shan *et al.* showing both numerically and

experimentally that multiple folding mechanisms were achievable in elastomeric structures comprising of triangular arrays and circular holes [8]. Further, Mihai and Goriely developed a finite element analysis procedure (successive decomposition procedure) in order to assess the mechanical behaviour of square and tubular cellular bodies [9]. It was shown that under uniaxial compression, axisymmetric (barreling) and asymmetric (buckling) modes were possible. The authors further commented on the importance of compressive cellular behaviour, as the primary loading condition of cellular structures in nature.

These studies have focused primarily on the different modes of collapse of different hyperelastic cellular structures and their potential for energy absorption has not been quantified. In this study we plan to begin to better establish the relationship between the topology of simple hyperelastic cellular structures and their energy absorption profiles when subject to large compressive strains. We also aim to investigate energy absorption diagrams, traditionally used to analyse the energy absorption capability of foams, for the analysis of hyperelastic macroscopic cellular structures.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3D PRINTING OF CELLULAR STRUCTURES

All the cellular arrays in this study were produced by fused deposition moulding (FDM) 3D printing of transparent Thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU). The TPU was produced by Fenner Drives Inc and acquired under the commercial name NinjaFlex; with the Ultimaker original used to produce the architectures. A prerequisite testing campaign was carried out to assess the effect of print parameters on specimen quality, with the optimised parameters being an 8.9mm/minute filament extrusion rate (3mm diameter filament), 0.2mm layer height, 12mm/second print head speed and melt temperature of 230 °C (where Differential Scanning Calorimetry confirmed max melt temperature before TPU degradation of 240±5 °C).

CELLULAR ARRAYS

The topology and potential dimensional variables of the unit cells under investigation are shown in Figure 2. In this study, hexagonal arrays of varying density were formed by altering only cell wall length l , whilst keeping all other dimensions constant. The density of cellular arrays formed from the re-entrant topology was varied only by altering angle θ . Table 1 shows the average dimensions for the individual unit cells for each specimen measured after printing. The relative density of the cellular arrays formed from these unit cells is found by dividing the density of the array (ρ^*) by the density of neat TPU (ρ_i). The hexagonal unit cells are identified by their cell wall length l (mm) and the auxetic samples by their internal angle θ (°).

Figure 2: Topological variables available for modification

Dimension	Hex 4.4	Hex 3.5	Hex 2.8	Aux 45	Aux 40	Aux 35	Aux 30
$t_h=t_l$ [mm]	0.81	0.81	0.84	0.69	0.68	0.7	0.69
θ [°]	60	60	60	45	40	35	30
l [mm]	4.4	3.5	2.8	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.5
h [mm]	–	–	–	11	11	11	11
ρ^*/ρ_t –	0.19	0.23	0.27	0.25	0.28	0.31	0.35

Table 1: Topological variables of unit cells

These unit cells were assembled into arrays as depicted in Figure 3, with the intention that they be compressively loaded in the z -direction. The four auxetic samples with internal angle, θ , between 30-45° all contained the same number of unit cells, where changes in θ directly influence sample length L and height H . Figures 3b and 3c show the principal print assemble orientations of the hexagonal unit cells, such that orthogonal uniaxial loading conditions could be investigated for arrays with equivalent relative density. Table 2 details the dimensions of the manufactured arrays and number of unit cells along the length and height. The arrays are identified herein by their unit cell name and, in the case of the hexagonal arrays, their loading condition b or c , with reference to Figure 3 e.g. Hex4.4b refers to a hexagonal array assembled from unit cells with a 4.4mm wall length, loaded compressively in the z -direction along edge with zigzag geometry.

Figure 3: Illustrative examples of the three types of arrays formed from the unit cells

Dimension	Aux 45	Aux 40	Aux 35	Aux 30	Hex 4.4b*	Hex 3.5b*	Hex 2.8b*	Hex 4.4c*	Hex 3.5c*	Hex 2.8c*
L [mm]	75	73.4	72.5	72.3	63.9	64.2	64.1	64.4	62.7	61.4
[cells]	9	9	9	9	5	11	13	8	10	12
H [mm]	32.7	30.2	27.3	24.3	37	29.6	33.9	32.1	32.1	32.3
[cells]	4	4	4	4	5	5	7	4	5	6
D [mm]	22.0	22.0	22.0	22.0	21.8	21.9	21.9	21.8	21.7	21.5

*the scripts b and c refer to the assembly patterns seen in Figure 3b and 3c respectively

Table 2: Details of the 10 samples manufactured, formed from the unit cells described in Table 1, assembled in the manner shown in Figure 3

PROPERTIES OF THERMOPLASTIC POLYURETHANE

It was hypothesised that, as well as being affected by the aforementioned print parameters, the properties of the printed material would likely be effected by print direction, relative to any loading. In order to investigate the effect of print direction on the stiffness and strength of 3D printed TPU, a series of tensile tests were carried out on TPU specimens printed 0° and 90° (Figure 4a) to the loading direction (in accordance with ASTM D412) [10] over strain rates ranging from 0.03-0.3s⁻¹.

It was found that for optimised print parameters the print direction had a significant effect on the stiffness and ultimate tensile strength of tensile test specimens. Figure 4b shows the stress strain results for 0° and 90° specimens tested at a strain rate of 0.03s⁻¹. The 0° specimens exhibited higher stiffness and up to 1.5 times the ultimate tensile strength of the 90° however the 90° specimens underwent a higher strain to failure of up to 760% compared to 560% due to a partial unravelling of the printed layers. This directional dependence may prove significant as more complex printed cellular structures are developed and loading occurs both through printed thickness as well as along the print direction (as in this study). Investigations into strain rate dependence of the material are ongoing and will likely have a significant effect on the strain rate response of cellular materials formed from it.

Figure 4: (a) illustration of printed test specimens and (b) stress-strain for 0° and 90° specimens with optimised print parameters at a strain rate of 0.03s⁻¹.

COMPRESSION TESTS OF CELLULAR STRUCTURES

All compression testing was carried out on an Instron 3343 Universal testing machine with a 1kN load cell. ASTM D575 [11] was used as reference in testing with modifications to the boundary conditions, sample size and loading rates used in order to gather sufficient data to generate insightful energy absorption diagrams. All compression plates and indenters were lubricated between tests to allow for “free” boundary conditions. To simplify the testing, the compression plates and indenters were also fabricated from 3D printed Polylactic acid (PLA) and securely mounted to the test machine. Figure 5(a-d) shows the four indenters along with their major dimension. No elastic deformation of the PLA plates or indenters was noted throughout the experiments.

Hexagonal specimens were loaded in compression with flat plates to a pre-specified maximum strain dictated by the sample density, then immediately unloaded at the same strain rate. This cycle was repeated 5 times for each sample at strain rates of 0.03, 0.95 and 0.3s⁻¹.with the different arrays being compressed to 0.75, 0.75 and 0.7 strain respectively. These strain limits were found by compressing dummy samples of the same density prior to testing, ensuring that these values did not exceed the limit loads of the machine or introduce plastic deformation of the samples..

Auxetic specimens were loaded in compression with flat plates in the same manner with Aux 45, 40, 35 and 30 compressed to a maximum strain of 0.65, 0.6, 0.55 and 0.5 respectively. Further compression tests were carried out on the Auxetic specimens in order to investigate cell collapse behaviour and energy absorption during local compression. The Auxetic specimens were loaded in the same cyclic manner and to the same maximum strains as for the flat plate tests; all local compression tests were carried out at a strain rate of 0.095s^{-1} .

Figure 5: Indenters used to investigate the effect of locally compressing auxetic specimens

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The aim of the compressive testing campaign was to generate Energy absorption diagrams, as proposed by Gibson and Ashby [1]. The formation of these diagrams can allow for the optimum material to be selected for a load case with a given energy, a peak allowable stress and known strain rate. The results here will help establish the suitability of these types of diagrams for the assessment of 3D printed, TPU, macroscopic cellular structures and whether they can be used to reveal how subtle variations in individual cell topology can affect energy absorption. The results shown here are all from the 5th compressive loading cycle.

COMPRESSIVE BEHAVIOUR OF HEXAGONAL ARRAYS

Figure 6a shows the compressive stress-strain behaviour of the hexagonal arrays Hex 4.4c, 3.6c and 2.8c at a strain rate of 0.03s^{-1} . The linear elastic, elastic buckling and cell densification regions can be observed for all specimens with an increase in sample density resulting in an increase in plateau stress. The area under each of the stress-strain curves is then redrawn in Figure 6b to give the three energy absorption curves for these samples. An envelope is plotted tangentially to the three curves where each point gives the peak stress and total energy absorbed by each sample, up to the point just before significant densification occurs.

The energy curve envelope is a useful design tool as it can provide a trace of the optimum density cellular structure, made from a single material, to choose for a load case at a particular strain rate when the impact energy and peak allowable stress are known [1]. It should be noted that the intended use for such design envelopes, developed by Gibson and Ashby [1] is to analyse foams of varying density. It is hypothesised that by varying the density of cellular structures via a range of different means (e.g. internal angle and wall thickness) envelopes with a range of gradients and magnitudes would likely result, for structures with the same relative density. The energy absorption envelopes can be normalised by dividing both Energy absorption (W) and Stress (σ) by the modulus of the material; although this practice is not applied here, this should in theory allow cellular structures constructed from different materials to be compared on the same pair of axes [1].

Figure 6: a) Compressive stress-strain behaviour of Hex 4.4c, 3.6c and 2.8c at strain rate 0.03s^{-1} (samples indicated by their respective relative densities* and edge loading condition shown) and b) Stress vs energy absorption for the samples with an envelope plotted at a tangent to the three curves

The energy absorption envelopes were plotted for type *b* and type *c* hexagonal samples at strain rates of 0.03, 0.095 and 0.3s^{-1} from their respective stress-strain curves. These envelopes were then plotted together in Figure 7a and 7b to form energy absorption diagrams; a series of images are inset within the figures in order to show the edge loading conditions of the sample and the cell collapse behaviour during compression. Three lines of constant relative density are also indicated on each Figure. These diagrams show the range of impact events that these cellular structures are optimally suited to dissipating with respect to maximum stress allowed to occur, the impact energy and impact strain rate.

It can be clearly seen when comparing the two figures that, despite displaying data for samples with the same cell topology and density, the orthogonal loading conditions have led to a significant shift in the envelopes. The hexagonal samples loaded in condition *c* absorb significantly more energy up to densification than for load case *b*, typically 44% for all samples and strain rates. The increased energy absorption was accompanied by a higher stress up to the point of densification, 42% on average. As indicated within the Figure 7, the cell buckling modes for the different loading conditions differ significantly (these modes are consistent for all densities) with the mode depicted in Figure 7b absorbing more energy up to a higher stress than for the mode in Figure 7a. The stress-strain data for the arrays with these loading conditions confirm that it is within the elastic collapse region that the difference in energy absorption occurs; this is indicated by the plateau region for condition *b* occurring at a relatively constant stress rather than steadily increasing as can be seen for load case *c* in Figure 6a.

Strain rate appears to effect samples under both loading conditions in a similar manner, with higher strain rates leading to increased energy absorption up to densification, coupled with an increase in stress. A range of strain rates over a number of orders of magnitude would be required in order to reliably establish the gradient of this trend. These preliminary results do however indicate that the higher density samples are more significantly affected by increased strain rate than the lower density samples and that the trends seen here are consistent with those seen in open cell foams [1].

Figure 7: Energy absorption diagrams for a) Hex 4.4b, 3.6b & 2.8b and b) Hex 4.4c, 3.6c & 2.8c. The stages of deformation for Hex 2.8b and 2.8c are inset in their respective graphs and the buckling modes of the individual cells shown in an expanded view.

GLOBAL COMPRESSIVE BEHAVIOUR OF AUXETIC ARRAYS

The same flat plate compression tests were carried out on the 4 auxetic samples as for the hexagonal samples. Figure 8a shows the stress-strain curves for the Aux 30-45 at a strain rate of 0.03s^{-1} and 8b shows the corresponding curves for energy absorbed. As for the hexagonal samples, it can be seen in 8a that a decrease in density (coupled in this case with an increase in angle θ) leads to densification at a higher strain, with curves for samples with successively lower density nested beneath these. The stress strain curves do however possess some significantly different characteristics from the regular hexagon arrays.

Firstly, the plateau regions of Aux 35, 40, and 45 all have a two stages stiffness response; an initial section with a gradient close to zero and then a region of increased gradient before final densification occurs. The reason for this two-stage plateau can be explained with the images in Figure 9a which show the progressive compression of sample Aux 45. At low strains, the cells begin to compress and a small negative Poisson's effect can be seen (2), upon further compression, due to the unsupported external vertical walls, the sample buckles globally (3) and regions of the cells collapse and densification occurs (4). As the compression continues, these regions continue to densify but due to the topology of the collapsed cells, further compression leads to a net force on each cell towards the centre of the sample (5). This force leads to a reversing of the global buckling of the sample before it is eventually re-centred and fully compressed (6). It is this global buckling densification and subsequent sliding contact that leads to this increase in stiffness of the sample along the plateau. The sliding of the individual cells also leads to an uneven stress strain curve up until densification. This global buckling and re-centring was seen in all but the Aux 30 sample whose successive compression can be seen in Figure 9b; in this case, only the deformation of the individual cell walls (b) and the subsequent densification (c) resist the compressive loading. We hypothesise that this global buckling occurs when the energy required to bend the individual joints in the cells exceeds that required to buckle the zigzag members that run vertically. The occurrence of this behaviour requires further investigation and characterisation whilst including numerous factors such as material composition, sample size as well as cell topology.

Figure 8: a) Compressive stress-strain behaviour of Aux 30, 35, 40 & 45 at strain rate $0.03s^{-1}$ and b) Stress vs energy absorption for the same samples.

Figure 9: a) Images depicting the progressive compression of sample Aux45 at a strain rate of $0.095s^{-1}$ to 0.6 strain. Images illustrate the buckling of the sample with unrestricted edge conditions and the successive recentering due to cell topology. In contrast, b) the compression of Aux30 at a strain rate of $0.095s^{-1}$ to 0.5 strain does not lead to global buckling of the sample.

As anticipated, the complex collapse behaviour leads to complex energy absorption behaviour (Figure 8b). Firstly, it should be noted that the energy absorption profiles of Aux 35, 40 and 45 are not smooth up to densification due to the contact and sliding of cells; this is in contrast to the absorption curve of Aux 30. It can also be observed that the absorption curve of the highest density sample, i.e. Aux 30, is nested beneath the lower density samples which is the reverse of the behaviour seen for the hexagonal samples; a result likely attributed to the presence of the mixed mode compression

behaviour. The trend for absorption curves Aux 35, 40 and 45 is less clear and therefore it is not possible or useful to attempt to create the traditional energy absorption envelope for these curves without investigating a larger number of samples with a larger range of angle θ . The trends seen in Figure 8 are reflected in results conducted for all compressive strain rates. Although an energy absorption diagram has not been formed for the auxetic samples, the envelope in which the auxetic data would reside has been indicated in Figure 7b. Despite all the auxetic samples possessing a higher relative density than the hexagonal samples, the apparent optimised envelope lies at a lower energy and higher stress, indicating that the topologies chosen here are in general less efficient for absorbing impact events.

LOCAL COMPRESSIVE BEHAVIOUR OF AUXETIC ARRAYS

Local compression tests were carried out on all auxetic samples with the indenters shown in Figure 4 at a strain rate of 0.095s^{-1} in the same cyclic manner as for the flat plate compression tests. Although force-displacement data for these tests was gathered, due to the development of contact area of the indenters with the sample, it is not possible to form comparable stress-strain curves without further visual processing of video data gathered. The general observation can be made however that the same trend exists for local indenters as for the flat plate compression that the lower density, higher angle structures, absorb more energy up to densification. Despite as yet not obtaining energy absorption diagrams for these structures, visual data gathered during experiments provides a useful means to assess the cellular collapse behaviour of the auxetic samples when subject to localised compression.

Figure 10(a-d) shows the compression of Aux 40 with the four indenters at 0, 0.3 and 0.6 compressive strain. For this sample which exhibited a global buckling response under flat plate compression, it can be seen that a reduced global response occurs for a narrower indenter. The global buckling of the specimen can be seen to be non-existent when the 20mm and bullet indenters are applied (10b, c). Further to this, the localised compression of the sample can be seen to lead to a gathering of the auxetic cells at the impact sight, drawing material from the surroundings and distributing the local load over a larger area of material. Further investigations will look into how this behaviour compares to the local compression of hexagonal structures.

Figure 10: Compressive behaviour of Aux 40 with indenters a) R=40, b) R=20, c) R=10 and d) R=5

4 CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

Cellular structures with energy absorbing capability have been successfully formed via the 3D printing of thermoplastic polyurethane. Energy absorption diagrams have proved a useful tool in establishing the effect of the scaling of cell size in hexagonal arrays. It was found that the introduction of a uniaxial compressive load, initiated orthogonally to the cellular architectures, leads to different local and global cell buckling modes, with the peak stress and energy absorption varying on average, 42% and 44% respectively, for the same density material. The auxetic structures subjected to the same loading conditions, exhibited a more complex collapse behaviour for unit cells when the internal/re-entrant angle $\geq 35^\circ$. It was observed, that global buckling of the vertical members occurred under compression however, due to the unit cell topology, the samples would self-realign under high compressive strains.

The results gathered in this study have provided a first stage insight into the effect of varying cell topological parameters on the elastomeric cellular structure's ability to absorb compressive energy. It will be necessary to investigate the effect of varying a large range of parameters at constant density in order to establish the optimal cellular structures for a range of impact events. Further, by subtly varying features of individual cells, which is made possible via the use of 3D printing, the compressive response of the auxetic samples may be favourably tailored. In addition to varying the cell topological variables on structural response and the role of geometric scaling, further work intends to investigate the tailoring of cell density through the sample thickness, in order to tailor the energy absorption behaviour during an impact event. This work will lead into the integration of these elastomeric cellular structures into flexible sandwich panels for structural energy absorption, the development of which is occurring concurrently alongside this work

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